

NONLINEAR BEHAVIOR OF CROSS-PLY LAMINATES UNDER TENSION AND ITS IMPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The classical bilinear theory is now obsolete. Details of the stress-strain diagrams of a glass/epoxy and a carbon/epoxy [0/90₅]_S laminate are explained. In these laminates, the behaviors are different and the failure modes are different. In the glass/epoxy laminates, tree-shaped cracking dominates. Stress distributions between transverse cracks that were derived from the 2-dimensional shear-lag analysis are shown. The distributions show stress concentrations at the tip of transverse cracks. The classical 1-dimensional shear-lag analysis failed to predict such stress concentrations. Improved failure mechanism is explained.

Keywords: fiber reinforced composites, tension tests, stress-strain diagrams, stress analysis, stress concentration, failure analysis, fracture mechanics

1. INTRODUCTION

From a standpoint of basic science, implications of nonlinear behaviors of a glass/epoxy and a carbon/epoxy cross-ply laminate under uniaxial tension will be explained in detail. In these two laminates, the failure processes are different. In particular, the glass/epoxy laminate is characterized by tree-shaped cracking. Improved concepts will be given for stress-strain diagrams, stress distributions between transverse cracks and mechanism of progressive failure.

2. STRESS-STRAIN DIAGRAMS

The bilinear theory of S. W. Tsai [1] is widely known through the textbook of R. M. Jones [2]. However, Tsai later on revised his theory twice [3,4]. Revisions were not stated explicitly in the papers. Figure 1 illustrates the differences of three theories according to the present author's interpretation. The large discrepancy of point Q is due to inappropriate use of the stiffness and the strength of filament. When recalculated using the values of a unidirectional composite, netting analysis gives final fracture point at point T. Line OT indicates simple elongation of the 0-degree layers and fiber breakage occurs at point T. In the third theory, a straight line is drawn from point P to point T, and continuous onset of transverse cracks was assumed up to

Figure 1. Three bilinear theories.

point T. The first theory is a plastic failure theory. Total failure of the 90-degree layer is assumed to occur at point P. This is the reason for the sudden decrease of the tangent modulus. Also it is assumed that the failure stress at point P of the 90-degree layer remains constant in that layer as a plastic stress. After point P, the remaining stiffness is that of the 0-degree layers only. Therefore line PR is parallel to line OT. Line PR indicates simple elongation of the 0-degree layers, and no additional failures can occur in the 90-degree layer. Glass/epoxy or carbon/epoxy composites are characterized by cracking. This plastic failure theory is inappropriate to use for such composites. It is said that Tsai's experiment agrees very well with this theory. But the experiment was conducted on one specimen only. Therefore the reliability of the experimental result is not certain.

The present author has made theoretical and experimental investigations on this subject extensively [5-18]. Important findings will be explained subsequently.

2.1. E-Glass/Epoxy [0/90₅]_s Laminate.

Figure 2 illustrates the stress-strain diagram of this laminate. This is the same laminate as that of Tsai [1]. As seen from the figure, the tangent modulus of the diagram decreases suddenly at point A. The diagram is convex after the knee. The diagram is almost straight after point B. Fiber breakage occurs at point C. Concentric lines are drawn from point O'. When the effect of curing temperature is neglected, this point coincides with origin O. The secant modulus is to be measured basing on

Figure 2. Stress-strain diagram of E-glass/epoxy [0/90₅]_s laminate.

be determined from the author's previous theory [5, 7, 8]. The percentages indicate failure extent of the 90-degree layer. The parentheses mean that the value is a rough estimate allowing for data scattering. The frequency distribution of transverse cracking is shown on the right. In the case of this material, transverse cracking occurs radically at point A, and then gradually diminishes. At point B, transverse cracking is finished [13, 14]. At the tip of each transverse crack, strong stress concentration arises, which induces small oblique cracks as illustrated [13, 14]. The author call this type of cracking the tree-shaped cracking. The long process from point B to point C is due to stable growth of oblique cracks that were produced previously. Without taking account of this tree-shaped cracking, the nonlinear behavior of glass/epoxy laminates cannot be explained. At point B, transverse cracks saturate with a sparse spacing. The author's estimate of the minimum aspect ratio of the spacing of transverse cracks is unity. The corresponding failure extent is roughly 60 percent. The high failure extent of about 90 percent at point C is due this tree-shaped cracking.

When unloading is performed from any point on the stress-strain diagram, all the unloading paths are straight and concentric with respect to point O'. The crack closure effect was not observed even when the applied load is decreased to almost zero. When the load is turned to be compression, all the transverse cracks will close, and the initial intact stiffness of the laminate will be recovered.

2.2. T300/Epoxy [0/90₅]_s Laminate

The stress-strain diagram of this laminate is illustrated in Figure 3. In this case, the diagram is characterized by concave variation after point A and the final fracture occurs at roughly 60 percent failure of the 90-degree layer. As shown by the frequency distribution curve, transverse cracking increases gradually and then decreases gradually. According to the author's experiment, the curve was a normal distribution. In all tests including laminates of thinner 90-degree layer, transverse cracking was almost saturating at final fracture, but yet not completely. Oblique cracks dominating in glass/epoxy laminates were not observed in carbon/epoxy laminates. Unloading characteristics are the same as those of the glass/epoxy laminate.

Figure 3. Stress-strain diagram of T300/epoxy [0/90]s laminate under tension.

In the case of the carbon/epoxy composite, the 0-degree layer shows a stiffening effect. When the relative thickness of the 90-degree layer becomes smaller than this laminate under consideration, this stiffening effect becomes not negligible. It is necessary to subtract this stiffening effect from the experimental data. Then the subtracted stress-strain diagram shows the same property as explained in Figure 3.

It seems the whole process of Figure 3 is comparable to the process of Figure 2 up to point B excluding the difference in the frequency distributions. At point B of both figures, the load ratios $(\sigma_x)_B/(\sigma_x)_A$ are the same order of magnitude. The failure extents are roughly the same. Transverse cracking is saturating there.

In glass/epoxy laminates, oblique cracks are produced. This will reduce the stress concentration at the tip of transverse cracks. It seems the interlaminar shear failure does not occur when preceded by oblique cracks.

3. STRESS DISTRIBUTIONS BETWEEN TRANSVERSE CRACKS

Before initiation of transverse cracks, the tensile axial stress is uniform in the 90-degree layer. When transverse cracks are produced, the stress distribution changes greatly. In conjunction with this topic, the so-called "modified shear-lag analysis" of K. W. Garrett and J. E. Bailey [19], which is essentially due to J. Aveston and A. Kelley [20], is generally known. In the paper, Garrett and Bailey provided a charming concept about progressive transverse cracking. This, however, is a 1-dimensional shear-lag analysis and cannot take account of the variation of stresses across the thickness of the 90-degree layer. Due to over-simplification of the analysis, derived results could be misleading. The stress distributions of this analysis are employed even in recent years, such as by Fukunaga, Chou, Peters and Schulte [21], and by Kobayashi, Ogihara and Takeda [22].

Figure 4. Definition of notations.

3.1. 2-Dimensional Shear-Lag Analysis

The present author reported a 2-dimensional shear-lag analysis previously [6, 9]. Definitions of notations are shown in Figure 4. The stress distributions in the quarter region of the 90-degree layer shown shaded are indicated in Figures 5 and 6. In both figures, the laminate

Figure 5. Stress distributions in E-glass/epoxy $[0/90]_s$ laminate by 1-dimensional shear-lag analysis.

Figure 6. Stress distributions in E-glass/epoxy $[0/90]_s$ laminate by 2-dimensional shear-lag analysis.

Figure 7. Stress distributions in T300/epoxy [0/90]s laminate by 2-dimensional shear-lag analysis.

is E-glass/epoxy [0/90]s. Figure 5 is derived by the 1-dimensional shear-lag analysis of Garrett and Bailey, and Figure 6 by the 2-dimensional shear-lag analysis of the present author. The axial stress and the shear stress distributions are shown for three different aspect ratios L/t_2 . Both the axial and the shear stresses are shown normalized by σ_{20} , which is the transverse strength of the 90-degree layer. Point C of Figure 4 is the tip of a transverse crack. In Figure 6, both the axial and the shear stresses show strong stress concentration at the crack tip as expected. As is obvious from Figure 5, the 1-dimensional shear-lag analysis gives misleading stress distributions. When the normalized axial stress becomes unity, a new transverse crack can be produced there. In Figure 6, the axial stress is nearly equal to unity along AB when $L/t_2 = 4$ and 2. This indicates that, once few transverse cracks are produced, many more transverse cracks will be produced immediately at a constant load or by slightly increased load resulting in quick reduction of the crack spacing. When $L/t_2 = 1$ is reached, the situation changes greatly. The axial stress at point A becomes very small. Therefore a new transverse crack cannot be produced any more from the vicinity of point A. A new transverse crack may be apt to be produced from point B. But it cannot grow as a transverse crack. Because of the stress distribution, the only possible mode is an oblique crack directed toward the nearby transverse crack.

In Figure 7, the axial stress distributions in the T300/epoxy [0/90]s laminate are shown. As compared with Figure 6, the effect of stress concentration is seen to be weaker. Also not shown, the shear stress distributions are similar to those of Figure 6.

3.2. Mechanism of Progressive Transverse Cracking

Figure 8 illustrates the distributions of axial stress along midthickness and along the interface with the 0-degree layer. The concept of Garrett and Bailey was derived referring only to the axial stress distribution along midthickness. According to their concept, the axial stress is greater where the crack spacing is larger. As the load is increased, the stress at location A reaches the critical value. A new crack is produced there and the crack spacing is halved. By further increase of load, the stress at location C reaches the critical value, and a new crack is generated there.

Figure 8. Stress distributions along midthickness and interface.

But referring to the stress distribution along the interface, it is evident that their concept is not appropriate. All the stresses along the interface are greater than the critical value. This may mean that transverse cracks can be produced from the interface anywhere any time. The stress is greatest at crack tips. If we call the transverse crack the primary failure, the stress concentration at the crack tip has a potential to cause some kind of secondary failure. One mode of the secondary failure is the commonly known interlaminar shear fracture which will occur in carbon/epoxy laminates. Another is the oblique cracks which occur in glass/epoxy laminates. Excluding the vicinity of crack tips, after the first cracking in the laminate, transverse cracks can be produced from anywhere. Therefore, the author attributes the progressive transverse cracking to the scattered strengths. At lower loads, transverse cracks occur here and there at weaker portions. At higher loads, stronger portions are cracked here and there. In this way, the crack spacing become smaller. When the aspect ratio of the crack spacing becomes unity, the stress distribution changes greatly as shown in Figures 6 and 7, and transverse cracking comes to saturation. We may think that the frequency distribution of figures 2 and 3 directly indicates scattered characteristics of transverse strengths of the 90-degree layer.

4. CONCLUSION

Comparing the nonlinear behaviors of a glass/epoxy and a carbon/epoxy cross-ply laminates under tension, differences in the failure processes and the failure modes is explained in detail. It is pointed out that the behavior of the glass/epoxy laminate is due to tree-shaped cracking. Stress distributions between transverse cracks derived by the 2-dimensional shear-lag analysis are compared with the results of the classical 1-dimensional analysis. A new concept is given for the mechanism of progressive transverse cracking.

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